

NDAC/LO/043

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REVIEW OF THE ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION AND SMS UPDATE

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0. Introduction

This review is based on the original process definition (NDAC/LO/014, 1982 Dec 28) but incorporating many new ideas and improvements suggested by F van Leeuwen (Development-progress report, 1983 Sept 9; rev 1984 Febr 28).

1. Coordinate triads

The primary celestial reference frame is the equatorial J2000.0 frame, represented by the triad $\underline{N} = [\underline{l} \quad \underline{m} \quad \underline{n}]$. $\underline{l}$ and $\underline{n}$ are unit vectors towards the mean vernal equinox and North equatorial pole, respectively, of the standard epoch, and $\underline{m} = \underline{n} \times \underline{l}$.

Two auxiliary reference frames may be derived from $\underline{N}$ by means of exact transformations: the ecliptical frame $\underline{K} = [\underline{l} \quad \underline{j} \quad \underline{k}]$ and the sun-oriented ("heliotropic") frame $\underline{S} = [\underline{s} \quad \underline{k} \times \underline{s} \quad \underline{k}]$. $\underline{k}$ is the unit vector towards the mean ecliptical pole of the standard epoch and $\underline{s}$ is the unit vector towards the "nominal sun" (Lindegren, 1984 April 17). The following exact relations hold:

$$\underline{K} = \underline{N} \underline{A}_1(\epsilon) \quad (1)$$

$$\underline{S} = \underline{K} \underline{A}_3(\lambda_s) = \underline{N} \underline{A}_1(\epsilon) \underline{A}_3(\lambda_s) \quad (2)$$

where

$$\epsilon = 23^\circ 26' 21''.448 \quad (3a)$$

$$\lambda_s = L + 2e \sin g + \frac{5}{4} e^2 \sin 2g \quad (3b)$$

$$L = -1.38691 + (0.0172021240/86400) T \quad (3c)$$

$$g = -0.04114 + (0.0172019696/86400) T \quad (3d)$$

$$e = 0.016714 \quad (3e)$$

and T is the time in seconds (TDT) from J1988.0 TDT = 1988 Jan 1, 12^h TDT.

The telescope frame is given by the triad $\underline{Z} = [\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z}]$, with $\underline{z}$ normal to the viewing directions and towards the solar-panel side of the satellite, and $\underline{x}$ bisecting the acute angle between the viewing directions. The precise definition of this frame follows from the definition of field angles (now superseded by the field coordinates w, z); see (Lindgren, 1984 April 30) and NDAC/LO/037.

$\underline{N}$ and $\underline{K}$ are obviously inertial frames (formally at least), while $\underline{S}$ and $\underline{Z}$ are not.

2. Attitude representation: definition of heliotropic angles

The term attitude in general refers to the orientation of $\underline{Z}$ with respect to $\underline{N}$. It is uniquely given by a (3,3)-matrix $\underline{A}$ such that

$$\underline{Z} = \underline{N} \underline{A} \quad (4)$$

The attitude matrix $\underline{A}$ is clearly orthogonal and has a six-fold redundancy. The non-linear relations among the elements of $\underline{A}$ make the matrix itself a somewhat awkward representation of the attitude, and we prefer to write it as the product of three (or more) elementary rotations, thus defining a non-redundant set of three attitude (Euler) angles. The decomposition is however by no means unique and the actual choice of attitude angles is to a great extent arbitrary and a matter of taste and convenience. It should only ensure that no ambiguity occurs (other than the trivial modulo 2π) and that no singularity or near-singularity is possible in the normal operation of the satellite. [A classic example of singularity is offered by the usual elements i, Ω, ω for the orientation of an elliptic orbit when the inclination becomes zero and Ω, ω undefined (although $\Omega + \omega$ is not). In this example, a possible ambiguity is furthermore resolved by the convention $i \geq 0$.]

The chosen representation is by means of the heliotropic angles ν, ξ, Ω :

$$\underline{Z} = \underline{S} \underline{A}_1(\nu - \frac{1}{2}\pi) \underline{A}_2(\frac{1}{2}\pi - \xi) \underline{A}_3(\Omega) = \underline{S} \underline{B}(\nu, \xi, \Omega) \quad (5)$$

so that the attitude matrix becomes

$$\underline{A} = \underline{A}_1(\varepsilon) \underline{A}_3(\lambda_s) \underline{B}(v, \xi, \Omega) \quad (6)$$

with

$$\underline{B}(v, \xi, \Omega) = \underline{A}_1(v - \frac{1}{2}\pi) \underline{A}_2(\frac{1}{2}\pi - \xi) \underline{A}_3(\Omega)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} s\xi c\Omega & -s\xi s\Omega & c\xi \\ -cv c\xi c\Omega + sv s\Omega & cv c\xi s\Omega + sv c\Omega & cv s\xi \\ -sv c\xi c\Omega - cv s\Omega & sv c\xi s\Omega - cv c\Omega & sv s\xi \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

With this representation, singularities occur for $\xi = 0$ and π , and there is an ambiguity as to the sign of ξ . Thus we must introduce the constraint

$$0 < \xi < \pi \quad (8)$$

If the satellite for some reason is operated in sun pointing mode ($\xi \simeq 0$), it will be necessary to modify our attitude representation. Perhaps the simplest way out would be to add a constant angle, of the order of $\frac{1}{2}\pi$ rad, to the nominal sun longitude in (6).

3. Nominal attitude

According to my proposal (1984 April 17), the nominal scanning law is directly expressed in terms of v, ξ, Ω as explicit functions of time (T). As a matter of computational convenience, it should only be pointed out that the Fourier series for $v(T)$,

$$v = \bar{v} + a_1 \cos \bar{v} + a_2 \sin 2\bar{v} + a_3 \cos 3\bar{v} + a_4 \sin 4\bar{v} \quad (9)$$

is more efficiently evaluated by the equivalent formula

$$v = \bar{v} + (b_1 + s(b_2 + s(b_3 + sb_4))) \cos \bar{v} \quad (10a)$$

where $s = \sin \bar{v}$ and

$$b_1 = a_1 + a_3, \quad b_2 = 2a_2 + 4a_4, \quad b_3 = -4a_3, \quad b_4 = -8a_4 \quad (10b)$$

The nominal attitude matrix, angles, etc shall be distinguished, whenever necessary, by means of the superscript ⁽ⁿ⁾.

4. Real-Time attitude

The on-board estimate of the attitude is updated at a nominal frequency of 0.9375 Hz (twice per frame). It consists of the three attitude error angles (Tait-Bryan angles) ϕ , θ , ψ , and possibly also their estimated time derivatives. The error angles are defined by means of the transformation

$$\underline{Z}^{(RT)} = \underline{Z}^{(n)} \underline{A}_1(\phi) \underline{A}_2(\theta) \underline{A}_3(\psi) \quad (11)$$

(SS.5.46.0, issue 3, section 3.1.2.6). The attitude control is such that these angles normally do not exceed 10° .

For determination of the reference attitude, it is required to express the RT attitude directly in heliotropic angles. From the nominal scanning law we have $\underline{B}^{(n)}$ according to (7) and then

$$\underline{B}^{(RT)} = \underline{B}^{(n)} \underline{A}_1(\phi) \underline{A}_2(\theta) \underline{A}_3(\psi) \quad (12)$$

from (11). From (7)-(8) it is seen that the heliotropic angles can be derived from the elements of $\underline{B}^{(RT)}$, viz.

$$\nu^{(RT)} = \text{ATAN2}(B_{33}, B_{23}) \quad (13a)$$

$$\xi^{(RT)} = \text{ATAN2}([B_{11}^2 + B_{12}^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}, B_{13}) \quad (13b)$$

$$\Omega^{(RT)} = \text{ATAN2}(-B_{12}, B_{11}) \quad (13c)$$

Alternative ways to calculate the heliotropic angles for the RT attitude can however be derived by elementary manipulations of (7) and (12). We find for instance

$$\sin \xi^{(RT)} \sin(\nu^{(RT)} - \nu^{(n)}) = c\Omega^{(n)} s\phi c\theta - s\Omega^{(n)} s\theta \quad (14a)$$

$$\sin \xi^{(RT)} \cos(\Omega^{(RT)} - \psi) = s\xi^{(n)} (c\Omega^{(n)} c\theta - s\Omega^{(n)} s\phi s\theta) - c\xi^{(n)} c\phi s\theta \quad (14b)$$

$$\sin \xi^{(RT)} \sin(\Omega^{(RT)} - \psi) = s\xi^{(n)} s\Omega^{(n)} c\phi - c\xi^{(n)} s\phi \quad (14c)$$

Thus, if the right-hand sides of (14a)-(14c) are denoted A, B, and C, respectively, we obtain the required angles from

$$D = \sqrt{B^2 + C^2} \quad (15a)$$

$$\nu^{(RT)} = \nu^{(n)} + \arcsin(A/D) \quad (15b)$$

$$\xi^{(RT)} = \arcsin(D) \quad (15c)$$

$$\Omega^{(RT)} = \Omega^{(n)} + \psi + \arcsin[(C \cos \Omega^{(n)} - B \sin \Omega^{(n)})/D] \quad (15d)$$

Comparison with eqs (7), (12), and (13) indicates substantial savings in the number of arithmetic operations and trigonometric evaluations, even when the matrix operations in (12) take full advantage of their sparseness. Another attractive property of the present method is that the RT attitude angles ν , Ω are obtained by adding a small angle ($\lesssim 10'$) to the nominal values. This ensures that the RT attitude angles are continuous with time, if the nominal angles are. In contrast, eqn (13) only gives the principal values of $\nu^{(RT)}$ and $\Omega^{(RT)}$, and additional tests are required to prevent discontinuities when these angles go through an odd multiple of π radians.

5. Reference attitude

The purpose of the reference attitude [distinguished by the superscript (0)] is to serve as a basis for linearizing observation equations of subsequent attitude refinements. It also provides the necessary input for SM Preprocessing (scan velocity, predicted time of transit). In order that linearization errors should be less than (say) $0''.01$, we must require that the errors of the reference attitude are less than some $(0''.01)^{\frac{1}{2}} \approx 45''$. For the prediction of SM transits, an accuracy of $1-2''$ is preferable, however. It would seem that this can easily be achieved by least-squares fitting suitable functions to the RT attitude data.

The reference attitude must furthermore be very smooth, even from the point of view of dynamical smoothing. This is necessary because subsequent attitude estimates, including the final one obtained after dynamical smoothing, are expressed in terms of small and smooth corrections to the reference attitude, e.g. in the form of splines. The functional model chosen for the reference attitude therefore should not permit any discontinuities except in the first (and possibly 0th) derivative of each attitude angle at the time of jet firings.

Thus, for an interval of several hours (e.g. between occultations), the reference attitude could be written in the form

$$v^{(0)} = v_{0\sigma} + v_{1\sigma}(T - T_0) + v_{2\sigma}(T - T_0)^2 + \sum_{\mu=1}^m \left[C_{v\mu} \cos \mu\Omega^{(n)} + S_{v\mu} \sin \mu\Omega^{(n)} \right] \quad (16)$$

and similarly for $\xi^{(0)}$ and $\Omega^{(0)}$. Here, σ is an index for each interval between jet firings and T_0 a suitable reference epoch for the occultation interval. Note that the second derivative of (16) is continuous throughout the occultation interval. The reference attitude is determined by means of a least-squares solution of the coefficients in (16), using $v^{(RT)}$, $\xi^{(RT)}$, and $\Omega^{(RT)}$ as observations, at a suitable spacing.

Note that the observation equations for the three attitude angles are identical except for the right-hand sides; the coefficient matrix need therefore only be reduced (triangularized) once. Note also that $\cos \mu\Omega^{(n)}$ and $\sin \mu\Omega^{(n)}$ are conveniently computed from the values $c\Omega^{(n)}$, $s\Omega^{(n)}$ already needed in (14)-(15). The calculation of heliotropic RT attitude angles should therefore be done simultaneously with the accumulation of normals (or Householder transformations).

6. First attitude reconstitution (AR1)

The attitude is now written as

$$v^{(1)} = v^{(0)} + \Delta v^{(1)} \quad (17)$$

(and similarly for $\xi^{(1)}$, $\Omega^{(1)}$), where $\Delta v^{(1)}$ is a spline function. The interval (σ) between two jet firings is subdivided into spline intervals (λ) separated by suitably spaced knots. If T_σ is some reference epoch near mid-time of the jet interval, we may introduce a relative time scale inside the interval,

$$\tau = T - T_\sigma \quad (18)$$

Spline interval λ is now defined as $\tau_\lambda \leq \tau < \tau_{\lambda+1}$, with $\lambda = 0$ being the interval containing $\tau = 0$, and $\Delta v^{(1)}$ is given by a particular polynomial

$\Delta v_\lambda(\tau)$ for each interval (dropping the superscript for the moment):

$$\Delta v(\tau) = \Delta v_\lambda(\tau), \quad \tau_\lambda \leq \tau < \tau_{\lambda+1} \quad (19)$$

The polynomials are of degree n ($= 3$, say), and strict continuity of the first $n-1$ derivatives at the knots is guaranteed by the following recursive definition of polynomials, starting from that of the middle interval:

$$\Delta v_0(\tau) = \Delta v_0 + \Delta v_1 \tau + \dots + \Delta v_n \tau^n \quad (\lambda = 0) \quad (20a)$$

$$\Delta v_\lambda(\tau) = \begin{cases} \Delta v_{\lambda-1}(\tau) + \delta v_\lambda (\tau - \tau_\lambda)^n & (\lambda > 0) \\ \Delta v_{\lambda+1}(\tau) + \delta v_{\lambda+1} (\tau - \tau_{\lambda+1})^n & (\lambda < 0) \end{cases} \quad (20b) \quad (20c)$$

The total number of coefficients determining the spline over the jet interval is $n + (\text{number of spline intervals})$.

In the following sections we derive the observation equations for the gyro signals and star mapper transits with Δv , $\Delta \xi$, $\Delta \Omega$ and their time derivatives as the attitude unknowns. In reality, the unknowns are of course the spline coefficients Δv , δv , etc in (20), but the required expansion of the observation equations is left implicit.

6.1. Gyro observation equations

There are three active gyros ($r = 1, 2, 3$), each sensing the inertial rotation about its input axis. Let $\underline{a}_r$ be a vector parallel to the input axis of the gyro and with $|\underline{a}_r|$ equal to the scale factor (output units per unit angular velocity). The gyro output is then

$$g_r = \underline{a}_r' \underline{\omega} + b_r(T) + \text{noise} \quad (21)$$

where $\underline{\omega}$ is the inertial rotation of the satellite and b_r the (low-frequency) drift rate (bias). Depending on the characteristics of the gyros, $b_r(T)$ may be assumed constant or linear with time over an occultation interval (TBC). We assume that the $\underline{a}_r$ are known from calibrations, and that any errors or variations of them can be absorbed into the bias term.

In terms of the heliotropic attitude angles, the inertial rotation can be written

$$\underline{\omega} = \underline{k} \dot{\lambda}_s + \underline{s} \dot{v} - \overbrace{(\underline{x} \sin \Omega + \underline{y} \cos \Omega)}^{\underline{z}} \dot{\xi} + \underline{z} \dot{\Omega} \quad (22)$$

With a_{rx} , a_{ry} , a_{rz} being the components of $\underline{a}_r$ in $\underline{Z}$ ($a_{rx} = \underline{x}' \underline{a}_r$ etc) and

$$a_{r1} = a_{rx} \cos \Omega^{(0)} - a_{ry} \sin \Omega^{(0)} \quad (23a)$$

$$a_{r2} = a_{rx} \sin \Omega^{(0)} + a_{ry} \cos \Omega^{(0)} \quad (23b)$$

the expected gyro signal (from the reference attitude and without bias and noise) is

$$\begin{aligned} g_r^{(0)} &= \underline{a}_r' \underline{\omega}^{(0)} \\ &= [(a_{rz} \sin \xi^{(0)} - a_{r1} \cos \xi^{(0)}) \sin v^{(0)} - a_{r2} \cos v^{(0)}] \dot{\lambda}_s^{(0)} + \\ &\quad + (a_{rz} \cos \xi^{(0)} + a_{r1} \sin \xi^{(0)}) \dot{v}^{(0)} - a_{r2} \dot{\xi}^{(0)} + a_{rz} \dot{\Omega}^{(0)} \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The term containing $\dot{\lambda}_s$ is quite small and it may be permitted to make some simplifying approximations for its evaluation. Perhaps fixed values for $\dot{\lambda}_s$ and for v , ξ inside the brackets can be used for the whole occultation interval. (Note that a_{r1} , a_{r2} are periodic with Ω , so that the bracket itself cannot be regarded as constant.)

The observation equation is then

$$\begin{aligned} (a_{rz} \cos \xi^{(0)} + a_{r1} \sin \xi^{(0)}) \dot{\Delta v} - a_{r2} \dot{\Delta \xi} + a_{rz} \dot{\Delta \Omega} + b_r + \text{noise} = \\ = g_r - g_r^{(0)} \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

in which b_r is possibly to be replaced by a small polynomial in $(T - T_0)$ and $\dot{\Delta v}$ etc are to be expressed in terms of the spline coefficient of (20). Considering the bandwidth of perturbations, it would seem sufficient to process one observation equation like (25) per gyro and per interval of 10 s or so. It is not obvious however that the non-linear variations of $g_r^{(0)}$ over such intervals of time are completely negligible, and it may be advisable e.g. to interpolate $g_r^{(0)}$ to the actual frequency of gyro readings (0.9375 Hz) before calculating an average O-C to be used on the right-hand side of (25).

6.2. Star Mapper observation equations

Using the reference attitude (A0), the Star Mapper count records are pre-processed to yield an observed transit time T_{gi} for star i across the centre line of the slitgroup labelled g . We also have an a priori knowledge of the equation of the centre line, $w = w_g(z)$. We shall now formulate an observation equation for this transit in which the unknowns are:

- (i) corrections to the reference attitude: $\Delta v, \Delta \xi, \Delta \Omega$
- (ii) corrections to the current star position: $\Delta \alpha \cos \delta, \Delta \delta$
- (iii) corrections to the centre line equation: Δw_g

Note that (i) are actually to be expressed in terms of the spline coefficients of (20) and (iii) perhaps as polynomials in z (NDAC/LO/040). The positional corrections (ii) refer to the star's barycentric equatorial coordinates at mission mid-epoch, (α_o, δ_o) .

For practical reasons, no rigorous solution is actually made for all the unknowns (i) - (iii). Rather, we effectively assume zero correlation between the different kinds of unknowns, and solve in the first instance the attitude unknowns with the assumption that all $\Delta \alpha \cos \delta = \Delta \delta = \Delta w_g = 0$. The residuals of this solution are then used by the SMSU process to obtain positional corrections to individual stars, and by an optional SM calibration process to obtain a solution for Δw_g .

At the observed transit time, T_{gi} , the proper direction of the star is $\underline{u}_{gi}$ and its components with respect to the equatorial frame, $\underline{N}'\underline{u}_{gi}$, are calculated by standard routines. Using the reference attitude, we also calculate the equatorial components of the auxiliary triad

$$\underline{E}^{(0)}(T_{gi}) = [\underline{e}_1 \quad \underline{e}_2 \quad \underline{z}] = \underline{N} \underline{A}_1(\epsilon) \underline{A}_3(\lambda_s) \underline{A}_1(v^{(0)} - \frac{1}{2}\pi) \underline{A}_2(\frac{1}{2}\pi - \xi^{(0)}) \quad (26)$$

[NDAC/LO/037, eqn (6)] and the trigonometric factors

$$C = \cos(\Omega^{(0)} + \frac{1}{2}f\gamma), \quad S = \sin(\Omega^{(0)} + \frac{1}{2}f\gamma) \quad (27)$$

in which f is the field index of the transit. The field coordinates of the star at time T_{gi} , as expected from the current position and reference attitude, can now be calculated as

$$w^{(0)} = -e_1 S + e_2 C, \quad z^{(0)} = \underline{z}' \underline{u}_{gi} \quad (28)$$

where

$$e_1 = \underline{e}'_1 \underline{u}_{gi}, \quad e_2 = \underline{e}'_2 \underline{u}_{gi} \quad (29)$$

As a matter of practical calculation, let $\underline{F} = \underline{N}' \underline{E}^{(0)}$ be the product of the four rotation matrices in (26). Then

$$\begin{bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \\ z^{(0)} \end{bmatrix} = \underline{E}^{(0)} \underline{u}_{gi} = \underline{E}^{(0)} \underline{N}' \underline{u}_{gi} = \underline{F}' (\underline{N}' \underline{u}_{gi}) \quad (30)$$

where $\underline{N}' \underline{u}_{gi}$ is the (3,1)-matrix containing the equatorial components of the proper direction.

The calculated position of the star in the field, $(w^{(0)}, z^{(0)})$, does not in general fall on the centre line of the slit group. The calculated distance, measured in the $+w$ direction, is

$$u_{\text{calc}} = w^{(0)} - w_g(z^{(0)}) \quad (31)$$

while the observed distance is $u_{\text{obs}} = 0$. The observation equation for the transit is therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u}{\partial v} \Delta v + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \xi} \Delta \xi + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \Omega} \Delta \Omega + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \alpha \cos \delta} \Delta \alpha \cos \delta + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \delta} \Delta \delta + \frac{\partial u}{\partial w_g} \Delta w_g + \text{noise} = \\ = -u_{\text{calc}} \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

with derivatives

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial v} = \left[z^{(0)} C + e_2 w_g'(z^{(0)}) \right] \sin \xi^{(0)} - v^{(0)} \cos \xi^{(0)} \quad (33a)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \xi} = -z^{(0)} S + e_1 w_g'(z^{(0)}) \quad (33b)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \Omega} = -v^{(0)} \quad (33c)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \alpha \cos \delta} = \underline{d}' \langle \underline{n} \times \underline{u}_{gi} \rangle \quad (33d)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \delta} = \underline{d}' (\underline{u}_{gi} \times \langle \underline{n} \times \underline{u}_{gi} \rangle) \quad (33e)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial w_g} = -1 \quad (33f)$$

Here,

$$v^{(0)} = e_1 C + e_2 S \quad (34)$$

is the projection of $\underline{u}_{gi}$ on the viewing direction (through the field centre), and therefore very close to unity, while

$$\underline{d} = -e_1 S + e_2 C - z w_g^{-1} (z^{(0)}) \quad (35)$$

is a vector of length $(1 + w_g^{-2})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ in a direction normal to the centre line and the viewing direction. For the calculation of (33d,e) it should be noted that the component column matrices for $\underline{n}$ and $\underline{d}$ in the equatorial frame are

$$\underline{N}' \underline{n} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \underline{N}' \underline{d} = \underline{N}' \underline{E}^{(0)} \underline{E}^{(0)}, \quad \underline{d} = \underline{F} \begin{bmatrix} -S \\ C \\ -w_g^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (36)$$

7. Second attitude reconstitution (AR2)

The purpose of AR2 is to improve (if necessary) the knowledge of Ω , i.e. of the spin about $\underline{z}$, to a degree sufficient for elimination of slit inconsistencies in the Set Solution. Recall that the requirement is that the relative error in Ω has a peak-to-peak value below half a slit period. It may be that this is in fact achieved already in AR1 when there is a sufficient number of accurate star positions available through previous SMSU. If this is not the case, the required improvement can be achieved by including IDT data in a second pass of the AR. The improved attitude is

$$v^{(2)} = v^{(0)} + \Delta v^{(2)}, \quad \xi^{(2)} = \xi^{(0)} + \Delta \xi^{(2)}, \quad \Omega^{(2)} = \Omega^{(0)} + \Delta \Omega^{(2)} \quad (37)$$

i.e. with $\Delta v^{(2)}$ replacing $\Delta v^{(1)}$, etc. AR2 is therefore merely an updating of the spline coefficients for A1 by inclusion of new observations.

The first attitude (A1) is input to the IDT Preprocessing and Location Estimator, where it is used e.g. to calculate the a priori smoothed grid coordinate at frame mid-time, $\tilde{G}_{ik} = \tilde{G}[\tilde{w}(T_k), \tilde{z}(T_k)]$, cf. NDAC/LO/035, eqn (4). The output is an estimate of the true smoothed grid coordinate at frame mid-time, which we may designate $\hat{G}_{ik}$. The difference, expressed in field coordinate along the scan,

$$\Delta w_{ik} = \left[\hat{G}_{ik} - \tilde{G}_{ik} \right] \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{G}}{\partial w} \right)^{-1} \quad (38)$$

is composed of errors due to the stellar position, attitude, large scale-distortion, and measurements. The positional error (Δp_i) remains constant, as the star moves across the FOV, and the measurement errors can be regarded as white noise (uncorrelated between frames). If distortion errors are neglected and we consider only attitude errors in Ω , we have therefore

$$\Delta \Omega^{(1+2)}(T_k) + \Delta p_i + \text{noise} = \Delta w_{ik} \quad (39)$$

which is an observation equation for the correction from $\Delta \Omega^{(1)}$ to $\Delta \Omega^{(2)}$ and the positional error. An observation equation in $\Delta \Omega^{(2)}$ is obtained by adding $\Delta \Omega^{(1)}$ on both sides,

$$\Delta \Omega^{(2)}(T_k) + \Delta p_i + \text{noise} = \Delta w_{ik} + \Delta \Omega^{(1)} \quad (40)$$

This could in principle be used as it stands for updating the attitude solution, but then we have to cope with the many new unknowns Δp_i . This can be avoided, and the number of observation equations very substantially reduced, by using the equations (40) for the FOV crossing of a certain star to estimate the time derivative of $\Delta \Omega^{(2)}$ only at the mean time of the crossing. This is done by means of a linear regression of the right member in (40) versus T_k for each crossing. In the regular case when the star is observed in nine consecutive frames, say $k = k_i - 4, k_i - 3, \dots, k_i + 4$, the unweighted estimate of the attitude error rate takes the particularly simple form

$$\dot{\Delta \Omega}^{(2)}(T_{k_i}) = (60\Delta T)^{-1} \sum_k (k - k_i) \left[\Delta w_{ik} + \Delta \Omega^{(1)}(T_k) \right] \quad (41)$$

where ΔT is the frame period.